

Terpenoids: Part XLIX. Synthesis of Methyl Ether of Debromolaurinterol

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1-Diazo-4-methyl-4-isopropenyl-4(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-2-butanone, a key intermediate in the synthesis, on decomposition in the presence of anhydrous copper sulphate in refluxing *n*-hexane yields 4,5-dimethyl-4(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-bicyclo(3.1.0)-hexan-2-one. This on subsequent submission to Wolff-Kischner reduction produces methyl ether of debromolaurinterol.

Debromolaurinterol (Ia), a sesquiterpene alcohol has recently been found in the seaweed of *L. intermedia* Yamada¹ variety as a minor constituent along with laurinterol (Ib). Structure (Ia) has been assigned to this compound on the basis of spectral data¹ and its relationship to aplysin (Ic)² via laurinterol, the constitution of the former being well established².

The salient features of the structure of debromolaurinterol (Ia) are the presence of a 2,4-disubstituted aromatic nucleus carrying a substituted cyclopentyl side chain fused to a cyclopropane moiety.

The properly substituted α -diazoketone (X), an important intermediate in the present synthesis, was envisaged to be converted through its copper-catalysed³⁻⁶ decomposition to the ketone (II). The latter compound could be transformed into methyl ether of

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debromolaurinterol (I) through the Wolff-Kischner reduction⁷. The various steps involved in the scheme are depicted below :

4-Methyl-2-methoxyacetophenone (III)⁸, the starting material in the above scheme was submitted to modified-Wittig reaction⁹ with 2,2'-diethyl-phosphonopropionate to give ethyl-2,3-dimethyl-3 (4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-acrylate (IV) in 70% yield. The compound (IV) when treated with lithium aluminium hydride¹⁰ afforded the carbinol (V) in good yield. The allylic alcohol (V) on refluxing with ethyl vinyl ether¹¹ in the presence of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate as catalyst furnished 2,3-dimethyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxyphenyl)-allyl vinyl ether (VI) which when submitted to Claisen rearrangement¹², in an atmosphere of nitrogen, gave 3-methyl-3-isopropenyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxyphenyl)-propan-1-al in 65% yield. The aldehyde (VII) on oxidation with silver oxide¹³ yielded 3-methyl-3-isopropenyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxyphenyl)-propionic acid (VIII) in almost quantitative yield. The acid (VIII) on refluxing with thionyl chloride in anhydrous benzene produced the corresponding acid chloride (IX) in high yield. The acid chloride on treatment with ethereal

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solution of diazomethane under usual condition³ generated α -diazoketone (X) which was subsequently decomposed with catalytic amount of anhydrous copper sulphate³ in refluxing *n*-hexane to give the desired ketone (II) in 65% yield. The ketone (II) on Wolff-Kischner reduction furnished the hydrocarbon (I) in 74% yield.

The identity of the compound (I), after chromatography over neutral alumina, was confirmed through its analytical data and N.M.R. and I.R. spectra.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis by B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar, Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. absorption spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid film.

Ethyl 2,3-dimethyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-prop-2-eneoate (IV): To a suspension of sodium hydride (6.0 g.) in diglyme (100 ml.) was added, dropwise and below 20° with constant stirring ethyl α -diethyl phosphono propionate (28.8 g.) and the solution was stirred until the gas evolution had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution, the ketone (III, 20.5 g.) was added slowly and at room temperature. After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 2 hrs. and then refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reaction mixture was decomposed with water and the product was extracted with ether (3 $\times$ 100 ml.). After drying over sodium sulphate, the solvent was removed and the residue on distillation under vacuum furnished α , β -unsaturated ester (IV, 21.7 g.) in 70% yield; b.p. 125–30°/10–12 mm. $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4258$. I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1740 (-ester), 815 and 705 cm^{-1} (substituted aromatic). (Found: C, 72.25; H, 7.84; Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$: C, 72.58; H, 8.06%).

2,3-Dimethyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-allyl alcohol (V): To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1.9 g.) in ether (250 ml.) was added, slowly and with stirring, the α , β -unsaturated ester (IV, 18.6 g.) in ether (125 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. After cooling, the mixture was decomposed with saturated sodium sulphate solution (100 ml.). The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous portion extracted with ether. The combined ethereal solution was washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation under reduced pressure furnished the carbinol (V, 10.5 g.) in 65% yield; b.p. 140–45°/10 mm. $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4452$. I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 3500 (-OH), 815 and 710 cm^{-1} . (substituted aromatic) (Found: C, 71.80; H, 8.02; calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$: C, 72.22, H, 8.38%).

2,3-Dimethyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-allyl vinyl ether (VI): A mixture of the allylic alcohol (V, 10.0 g.), ethyl vinyl ether (80 ml.) and mercuric acetate (1.0 g.) was refluxed for 10 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and stirred with sodium carbonate solution (10%, 25 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The organic layer was separated, washed with water and dried over potassium carbonate. Evaporation of the solvent and distillation of the residue under diminished pressure gave the vinyl ether (VI, 9.1 g.) in 80% yield; b.p. 120–22°/10–12 mm. $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4434$. I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1645, 1620, 1200 (vinyl ether), 815 and 710 cm^{-1} (substituted aromatic). (Found: C, 77.21; H, 8.32; calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$: C, 77.59; H, 8.62%).

3-*Methyl-2-isopropenyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-propan-1-al (VII)*: Vinyl ether (VI, 9.0 g.) was heated, under nitrogen and in a fully immersed half filled sealed tube, in an oil bath at 200°. After cooling, the contents were fractionated under diminished pressure to furnish the aldehyde (VII, 6.0 g.) in 65% yield; b.p. 130–34°/12 mm. $\frac{19}{D} \eta = 1.4398$. I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 2750 (aldehydic C–H), 1740 ($> C = O$) and 890 (triply substituted double bond), 815 and 710 cm^{-1} (substituted aromatic). The aldehyde (VII) afforded a yellow 2 : 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative melting at 145–47°. (Found : N, 13.32; calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4$: N, 13.66%).

3-*Methyl-3-isopropenyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-propionic acid (VIII)*: To a solution of the aldehyde (VII, 7.5 g.) in ethanol (215 ml.) and silver nitrate (6.2 g.) in water (150 ml.) was added, with stirring and over a period of 1 hr. a solution of sodium hydroxide in water (310 ml.). After stirring for 3 hrs. at room temperature the reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate concentrated in vacuum. The unreacted material was taken up in ether. Acidification in the cold of the aqueous solution with dilute sulphuric acid gave the acid as a thick oil which was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent and distillation of the residue under reduced pressure gave the acid (VIII, 5.6 g.) in 65% yield; b.p. 160–62°/10–12 mm. $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4954$. (Found : C, 72.25; H, 7.82; calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$: C, 72.59; H, 8.08%).

4-*Methyl-4-isopropenyl-3(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-propanoyl chloride (IX)*: A solution of the acid (VIII, 5.0 g.) in benzene (50 ml.) and thionyl chloride (3.0 g.) was heated under reflux till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. Excess of the thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and the residue on distillation furnished the acid chloride (IX, 4.2 g.) in 82% yield, b.p. 130–32°/10 mm.

4,5-*Dimethyl-4(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-bicyclo (3.1.0) hexan-2-one (II)*: The acid chloride (4.0 g.) in ether (100 ml.) was slowly added to an ice-cold solution of diazomethane (0.1 mole) in ether (250 ml.). The contents were allowed to stand at room temperature for 3 hrs. After the evaporation of the solvent, the diazoketone (X) obtained as a yellow oil was used without further purification for the next reaction. I.R. spectrum : 2100, 1620 cm^{-1} (characteristic of α -diazoketone³).

The α -diazoketone (X) dissolved in *n*-hexane (300 ml.), was treated with anhydrous copper sulphate (1.0 g.) and refluxed for 18 hrs. The solvent was removed and the ketone (II) thus obtained was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 140–45°/12 mm. $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4846$. I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1715 ($> C = O$), 3080, 1025 (cyclopropane), 815, 710 (substituted aromatic) and other peaks at 2950, 1600, 1575, 1500, 1475, 1350, 1285, 1200, 1190, 1150, 1085, 935, 860 and 760 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 78.29; H, 7.94; calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$: C, 78.68; H, 8.20%).

4,5-*Dimethyl-4(4'-methyl-2'-methoxy phenyl)-bicyclo (3-1.0)-hexane : methyl ether of debromolaurinterol (I)*: Hydrazine hydrate (100%, 2 ml.) was added to diethylene glycol (40 ml.) and ethylene glycol (10 ml.) containing the ketone (II, 1.0 g.). The mixture was heated at 184° for 1.5 hrs. After cooling to 70°, sodium (1.0 g.) in diethylene glycol (10 ml.) was added. The mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hrs. and then poured into iced-water.

Extraction with light petroleum ether (40–60°) and removal of the solvent gave the hydrocarbon (I, 0.7 g.) in 74% yield after purification by chromatography over neutral alumina (elution with petroleum ether 40–60°). I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 3060, 1025 (cyclopropane), lit.¹ reports (3060, 1025), 815, 710 (substituted aromatic) and other peaks at 2950, 1600, 1580, 1500, 1480, 1350, 1285, 1200, 1185, 1145, 1085, 935, 860 and 750 cm^{-1} .

The structure of the synthetic hydrocarbon was further confirmed by its N.M.R. spectrum which showed characteristic signals at $\tau = 7.70$ (3H, aromatic $-\text{CH}_3$ group), 8.66 and 8.72 (each 3H, 2 tertiary $-\text{CH}_3$ groups) and 9.48, 8.9 (2H, 1H, cyclopropane ring), lit.¹ reports $\tau = 7.78, 8.66, 8.72, 9.48$ and 8.9. (Found : C, 83.12; H, 9.28; calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$, : C, 83.40; H, 9.56%).

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